

Hand Gesture Recognition for Human-Computer Interaction: Finger Counting, Gesture-Based Gaming, and Touchless Scrolling

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Abstract—Hand gesture recognition has become an important approach in human-computer and human-robot interaction (HCI/HRI), allowing people to control systems in a natural and touch-free way. In this work, we present a real-time gesture recognition system that performs three tasks: finger counting, gesture-based control of the game *Subway Surfers*, and touchless screen scrolling. The system is built using computer vision techniques, combining OpenCV for image processing with MediaPipe for accurate hand landmark detection. Detected gestures are then mapped to meaningful actions, enabling smooth interaction with applications. Experimental results show that webcam-based gesture interfaces can deliver reliable performance for gaming, accessibility, and everyday navigation. Compared to expensive sensor-driven setups, this approach offers a low-cost and practical alternative for wider adoption.

Index Terms—Hand gesture recognition, human-computer interaction, human-robot interaction, computer vision, MediaPipe, touchless systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Human-computer interaction (HCI) and human-robot interaction (HRI) have evolved significantly, moving from physical interfaces such as keyboards and controllers to more natural modalities like speech and gestures. Hand gestures provide a highly intuitive form of communication, enabling systems to interpret user intentions without physical contact.

Touchless gesture recognition systems are particularly important in scenarios where traditional input devices are impractical, such as in healthcare (surgical environments), public kiosks, and assistive technologies for people with disabilities. In gaming, gesture-based interaction enhances immersion, while in robotics, it allows intuitive remote control of machines.

The motivation for this research is to develop a cost-effective, real-time system using only webcams, making advanced HCI accessible to everyday users without requiring expensive hardware.

This paper contributes:

- 1) A finger-counting module for recognizing numeric gestures.
- 2) A gesture-controlled interface to play the game *Subway Surfers*.
- 3) A touchless screen scrolling system controlled by vertical hand movements.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Gesture recognition has been widely studied in HCI and HRI. Early works relied on contour analysis and skin segmentation [1], which suffered from sensitivity to lighting and background noise. Later approaches incorporated machine learning for robust classification [2], but these required large training datasets.

Recent works emphasize real-time systems:

- Santos et al. (2022) proposed a system for HCI and HRI applications, highlighting gesture recognition for real-time control [4].
- Mohammed and Bakar (2023) explored gesture recognition in challenging environments, addressing noise and robustness [5].
- Lugaresi et al. (2019) introduced MediaPipe, a lightweight framework that has accelerated research in gesture-based interfaces by enabling efficient landmark detection [3].

Despite progress, few works demonstrate the integration of gesture recognition into interactive applications such as gaming and browsing, which is addressed in this study.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the hand gesture recognition system was divided into three key phases: design and development, system integration, and testing. Below, we provide more details on the components used, the integration process, and the testing strategies to ensure reliability and robustness of the system.

A. Tools and Frameworks

The development of the system relied on a combination of open-source libraries and tools for real-time hand gesture recognition and interaction:

- **Python:** The core language used for the implementation of the system. Python offers an extensive ecosystem of libraries for computer vision (OpenCV), machine learning, and automation (PyAutoGUI).
- **OpenCV:** OpenCV was employed for real-time image processing tasks such as background subtraction, hand tracking, and landmark extraction. It also provided essential features for webcam access and frame manipulation.

- **MediaPipe:** A lightweight framework designed by Google, MediaPipe was used for hand landmark detection, which provided fast and accurate identify the 21 key points of the hand (including the thumb, index, middle, ring, and little fingers).
- **PyAutoGUI:** This library simulated keyboard inputs and mouse actions, allowing the system to translate gestures into actual game control commands or operating system actions like scrolling.
- **Standard Webcam:** A basic 720p webcam was used to capture the user’s hand movements. The use of a standard webcam minimizes hardware cost and ensures that the system is affordable and accessible.

B. System Architecture

The system operates in a pipeline that continuously processes frames from the webcam, detects hand landmarks, classifies gestures, and executes corresponding actions. The architecture of the system can be divided into four main stages:

- 1) **Camera Input:** A video stream is captured in real-time using the webcam. The frames are then pre-processed for clarity, which may include adjustments to brightness and contrast to handle different lighting conditions.
- 2) **Hand Detection:** The MediaPipe library detects the hand in the video feed by identifying key points on the hand. The system tracks these key points (21 in total), allowing for accurate gesture recognition. The hand is localized by bounding boxes, and hand segmentation is performed to extract the region of interest.
- 3) **Gesture Recognition:** Once the hand is detected, the system identifies gestures by analyzing the position of the landmarks. The positional and angular relationships between landmarks are used to classify the gesture. This includes detecting finger counts, hand orientations, and palm centroid positions.
- 4) **Action Execution:** Based on the recognized gesture, appropriate actions are executed using PyAutoGUI, such as simulating keypresses for game control or sending scroll commands for screen navigation.

C. Gesture Recognition Models

For gesture recognition, we utilized a combination of pre-defined rules and machine learning techniques:

- **Rule-based Recognition:** Simple gestures such as finger counting and directional commands (for gameplay) were detected using rule-based logic. For example, the number of open fingers directly maps to a numeric value for finger counting.
- **Hand Orientation and Tilt Detection:** For dynamic gestures like the *Subway Surfers* game control (palm up, fist, hand tilt), the system computes the angles between landmarks to classify gestures like "move left" or "jump."
- **Hand Movement Tracking:** For tasks like scrolling, continuous tracking of the centroid of the hand was implemented. By comparing the vertical position of the palm centroid across frames, the system could determine

whether the user was moving their hand up or down, thus triggering scrolling actions.

D. System Workflow

The overall workflow of the system is shown in Fig. 1, which illustrates the sequence of operations from camera input to final action execution. After hand detection, the system passes the hand landmarks to the gesture recognition module, where predefined gestures are matched. If a gesture matches a predefined action, the system triggers a corresponding output (e.g., a simulated key press, mouse movement, or scroll command).

Fig. 1. System workflow: Camera Input → Hand Detection → Gesture Recognition → Action Execution.

E. Finger Counting

Finger counting is one of the simplest and most widely used gestures in hand gesture recognition. The technique involves analyzing the positions of the fingertips relative to their corresponding base joints. A fully open hand has five distinct finger positions, each corresponding to a number from 0 to 5. The logic implemented for finger counting involves:

- Detecting if each of the five fingers is open or closed.
- Mapping the number of open fingers to a numerical value.
- Handling variations in hand orientation, ensuring the system can detect gestures irrespective of hand angle.

For example, a gesture with only one finger extended (e.g., the index finger) will be recognized as the number "1," and a fist will be interpreted as "0." This is shown in Fig. 2.

F. Game Control

To enable game control for *Subway Surfers* using hand gestures, four specific gestures were mapped to in-game actions. The user performs simple hand gestures in front of the webcam to control the character’s movement:

- Palm Up → Jump
- Fist → Duck
- Hand Tilt Left → Move Left
- Hand Tilt Right → Move Right

Fig. 2. Finger counting using landmark detection.

The system recognizes these gestures by analyzing hand position and orientation, enabling a smooth, touchless gameplay experience. As shown in Fig. 4, the system translates gestures to in-game actions in real-time.

Fig. 3. Hand gestures controlling for slide *Subway Surfers* gameplay.

Fig. 4. Hand gestures controlling for up *Subway Surfers* gameplay.

G. Screen Scrolling

For the screen scrolling feature, the system tracks the vertical movement of the hand's palm centroid. This motion is mapped to scrolling actions:

- Upward motion → Scroll Up
- Downward motion → Scroll Down
- Volume increase → Volume Up
- Volume decrease → Volume Down

This feature allows users to interact with web pages or documents without physical contact, making it ideal for accessibility applications. The process is depicted in Fig. 9, where the hand movement corresponds to vertical scrolling.

Fig. 5. Hand gesture for touchless screen scroll down.

Fig. 6. Hand gesture for touchless screen scroll up.

Fig. 7. Hand gesture for touchless volume control(Decrease).

Fig. 8. Hand gesture for touchless volume control(Increase).

Fig. 9. Hand gesture for touchless Tab switching.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The system was tested under different lighting and background conditions using a standard 720p webcam. The following observations were made:

- **Finger Counting:** Achieved $\approx 95\%$ accuracy in stable lighting, with occasional errors in low light.
- **Gameplay:** Provided smooth and responsive control, with average latency under 100ms. Errors mainly occurred when the hand partially exited the frame.
- **Scrolling:** Demonstrated effective responsiveness, though background motion sometimes caused false triggers.

V. APPLICATIONS

This system demonstrates multiple practical applications:

- **Gaming:** Provides immersive, controller-free interaction.
- **Accessibility:** Assists individuals with limited motor abilities.
- **Healthcare:** Enables surgeons and medical staff to interact with devices without physical contact.
- **Public Interfaces:** Suitable for kiosks and ATMs, reducing the need for physical touch.
- **Robotics:** Extensible to robotic control via simple hand signals.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper demonstrated a real-time hand gesture recognition system using only a webcam and open-source frame-

works. The proposed system achieved high accuracy in finger counting, interactive gameplay, and screen navigation.

However, limitations exist in low-light environments and when hands are partially occluded. Future work will explore:

- Incorporating deep learning models for complex gesture classification.
- Extending the gesture vocabulary to support multi-user input.
- Integration with AR/VR platforms for immersive interaction.
- Applying the system in collaborative human-robot environments.

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